

THE "CA" IMPACT

SOC accumulation due to CA was 12% greater compared to conventional agriculture. In soils with less than 40 Mg C/ha the increment reached 20%

WHAT INFLUENCES THE ACCUMULATION OF SOC UNDER CA

SOC content – clay – rainfall – temperature – latitude- experiment duration

(SOC)KING OUT DESERTIFICATION

47 studies were quantitatively summarized by using a meta-analysis. Selected areas are highly vulnerable to the risk of desertification in the future.

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AUTHORS

Tommaso Tadiello, Marco Acutis, Alessia Perego, Calogero Schillaci, Elena Valkama (2022)

SOIL ORGANIC CARBON (SOC) UNDER CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE (CA) META-ANALYSIS IN MEDITERRANEAN AND HUMID SUBTROPICAL CLIMATES

Conservative approach

With a base annual increment of 0.48 tons carbon per hectare and year, a reasonable carbon gain can be enhanced with long term CA application. During this period, it is recommended to apply no-tillage management, retain residues on the top of the soil, and include as many (different) crops as possible in the rotation.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME ΣOMMIT

The SOMMIT project will evaluate trade-offs and synergies between soil C sequestration, nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses as affected by soil management options aimed at increasing soil C storage.

PROJECT COORDINATOR:

Alessandra Lagomarsino

alessandra.lagomarsino@crea.gov.it

TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Understanding of soil management for climate change mitigation, adaptation, sust production & sustainable environment

Understanding soil carbon sequestration and its contribution to climate change mitigation

Mission SOIL: Reduce desertification, Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL project
ΣOMMIT

Applicability:
Mediterranean South, -North and -Mountains
climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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